

Non-destructive dendrochronology with X-ray computed tomography: The influence of different conservation methods for waterlogged archaeological wood

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ABSTRACT

In this study, the influence of different conservation methods for waterlogged archaeological wood (WAW) on non-destructive dendrochronological dating by micro-computed tomography (μ CT) was evaluated. For this purpose, samples of different wood species were conserved using the following methods: alcohol-ether-resin, Kauramin 800®, lactitol/trehalose, saccharose, silicone oil and different polyethylene glycol (PEG) treatments with subsequent freeze-drying. The tree ring measurements of all samples in the digital μ CT data were compared with the measurements on an analog linear measuring table in terms of the total number of rings per sample and the mean ring width. The year-to-year ring width measurements in the μ CT data agreed very well overall with the corresponding microscopic measurements. It was possible to detect the rings in the samples with μ CT in all cases. A dendrochronological cross dating with regional absolutely dated ring width chronologies was successful in two cases. However, the different influence of the conservation agents on the quality of the μ CT data was clearly visible. In order to assess this influence, the contrast in the μ CT data was determined using grey-scale profiles. A decrease in contrast in the μ CT data was detectable for all conservation agents. A particular strong influence is observed for the conservation methods using silicone oil, lactitol/trehalose, PEG and saccharose. Overall, the study performed confirms that μ CT is a powerful and accurate method for non-destructive dendrochronology of conserved archaeological objects.

1. Introduction

In the temperate zone, archaeological objects made of wood are preserved mainly under waterlogged and anoxic conditions, where microbial decay is slowed down, and the wood structure is more or less completely filled with water. If waterlogged archaeological wood (WAW) is left to dry in an uncontrolled manner after excavation, it may collapse and shrink. Depending on the degree of degradation this can result in a complete loss of the object's original form and information. A lot of methods and conservation agents have already been tested for the conservation of WAW. In addition, there were several studies which aimed to compare the efficiency of the conservation methods (Christensen et al., 2012; Walsh et al., 2014, 2017; Broda and Hill, 2021; Stelzner et al., 2022). Since plants adapt to environmental conditions

during their lifetime and store this information in their tissues, wooden objects contain important evidence for archaeological research. This information enables the reconstruction of the living conditions of trees. Archaeological wood therefore offers an archive for interdisciplinary research. Ecological, economic, vegetation-historical, climatic and cultural-historical questions can be investigated. Furthermore, dendrochronology is a widely used, reliable and very accurate method for dating archaeological wood finds and thus an indispensable tool for archaeological research (Schweingruber, 2001; Baillie, 2002; Hughes, 2002; Speer, 2010; Billamboz, 2014). In general, the width of the annual rings is measured on the cross-section with an accuracy of 1/100 mm (Westphal and Heußner, 2016). If the outermost annual ring has been preserved under the bark (waney edge), both the felling date and the felling time can be determined (Sass-Klaassen et al., 2008). In

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conventional dendrochronological dating, the artifact must be sawed or drilled with an increment borer in order to get a cross section and measure all tree rings. This contradicts the requirements of conservation, which pursues the aim of preserving the object unchanged and as a whole. Similarly, the preparation of cross-sectional surfaces with a razor blade for dendrochronological dating is an invasive intervention in an artifact (Sass and Eckstein, 1994; Kuniholm, 2001; Bräker, 2002; Westphal and Heußner, 2016).

Among the currently available non-destructive methods, X-ray computed tomography (CT) is a suitable technique that allows the entire volume of a sample to be examined at various spatial resolutions (Withers et al., 2021). The method provides promising information to archaeological sciences in the field of dendroarchaeology, including conservation science (Stelzner et al., 2021, 2022). Not only is it non-invasive, but it requires almost no sample preparation and allows both qualitative and quantitative three-dimensional tree ring analyses (Van den Bulcke et al., 2014; Martínez-García et al., 2021, 2022). For these reasons, CT has enabled significant progress towards a non-destructive technique in the field of dendrochronology, both for wooden cultural heritage (Okochi, 2016; Daly and Streepton, 2017; Bossema et al., 2021; Domínguez-Delmás et al., 2021) as well as dendroecology and forest sciences (Maes et al., 2017; Vannoppen et al., 2017). The first attempts at non-destructive dendrochronological dating based on CT images were made as early as the 1980s (Onoe et al., 1984). However, sufficient resolution for non-destructive analysis and successful dating of wood samples was not achieved until the development of industrial μ CT (Okochi et al., 2007). As a result in dendroarchaeology, for example, the oak figures from Fellbach-Schmidlen could be dated to 127 ± 10 BCE (Keefer et al., 2006) and the oak figure from Eschenz to 9 ± 10 BCE (Belz et al., 2008). In addition, Grabner et al. (2007, 2009) succeeded in dating archaeological objects from the Hallstatt archaeological site made of fir (835 BCE, no waney edge), beech (1378 BCE, waney edge dating), and silver fir (1362 BCE, no information about the waney edge). Furthermore, dendrochronology of wood in blocks of soil was investigated using μ CT (Stelzner and Million, 2015), which allowed dating of oak fragments (500 CE, no waney edge). Kastner et al. (2007), Grabner et al. (2007, 2009), Bill et al. (2012), and Stelzner and Million (2015) similarly reported on the limitations of measuring ring widths, as image resolution depends on object size. In a large-scale study of more than 90 oak objects, Bill et al. (2012) confirmed the potential of μ CT for nondestructive dendrochronological analyses. Only six objects could not be dated. However, an important factor affecting the validity of the results is the condition of the objects. For example, the waterlogged finds investigated by Bill et al. (2012) had already been air-dried, as the measurements of the waterlogged wood and the samples impregnated with high molecular weight polyethylene glycol (PEG) did not provide sufficient contrast for a measurement of the tree ring widths. The difficulty of non-destructively dating of conserved WAW using μ CT was confirmed by Wiesner et al. (2016) in the case of a prehistoric wheel made of maple. This was conserved with 40% PEG 2000 with subsequent freeze-drying. In contrast, Daly and Ebert (2021) successfully dated a lid of an oak barrel from Odense, Denmark, conserved with 38% PEG 2000 and freeze-drying, to 1332 CE (no waney edge) based on 217 measured tree rings. Apart from this object, the figure from Eschenz, which was conserved using the alcohol-ether-resin method (Belz et al., 2008), and the figures from Fellbach-Schmidlen, which were conserved using obsolete materials such as Lyofix (Keefer et al., 2006), no conserved archaeological objects have been dated using CT. For this reason, Bill et al. (2012) also recommended that further experiments with CT and conserved wood for dendrochronology should be performed. The conservation of an artifact aims primarily to bring the object to a state of long-term chemical stability and to achieve homogeneous mechanical stabilisation of the structure. However, when WAW is conserved, there is a risk that the treatments will interfere with future non-destructive dendrochronological analyses with CT. Especially due to the difficulty of analysing WAW in its wet state before drying, the question arises

whether the structural information of the historical sources is still accessible and analyzable after conservation. The aim of this study was therefore to determine which common conservation methods allow non-destructive dating with μ CT and what impact these methods have on the visibility of the tree rings of different wood species in the μ CT data. To verify the results of the tree ring width measurements, they were compared with analogous conventional tree ring measurements under the stereomicroscope.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Samples

Within this study, conserved wood samples from different periods from the scientific reference collection of the Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie (LEIZA, former Römisch-Germanisches Zentralmuseum, RGZM) in Mainz, Germany, could be examined. The collection was built between 2008 and 2011 and consists of large archaeological finds from Central European excavation sites with different wood types and degrees of degradation. These objects were then cut into several samples of the same size and impregnated using the most common conservation methods at that time (Wittköpper et al., 2016; Stelzner et al., 2022). The samples were conserved at different institutions with their standard methods (Appendix A): alcohol-ether-resin (Bräker et al., 1979, Schmidt-Ott et al., 2022), melamine-formaldehyde (Kauramin 800®) (Wittköpper, 1998), lactitol/trehalose (Imazu and Morgós, 2002), saccharose (Parrent, 1985), silicone oil (Smith, 2003) and polyethylene glycol (PEG) with subsequent freeze-drying. PEG treatment followed either a one-step process with PEG 2000 (Jensen et al., 2011), two-step with PEG 400 and PEG 4000 (Cook and Grattan, 1990) or three-step with PEG 400, PEG 1500 and PEG 4000 (www.rgzm.de/kur). The degree of degradation was determined by the maximum water content (U_{max} in percent and their physical density in g/cm³ (Stelzner et al., 2022). A detailed overview of the conservation methods and the samples is given on the project homepage (www.rgzm.de/kur). For the analyses in this study, the ten largest test series of the collection were selected to cover a high variety of methods and wood genera. Since oak is the most important wood species for dendrochronology in Europe (Towner, 2002; Haneca et al., 2009), three oak series (Oa1, Oa2, Oa3) were chosen (Stelzner et al., accepted). In addition, another ring-porous wood species, ash (As1), was selected (Appendix B). Two diffuse-porous woods, alder (Al1) and beech (Be1), were also investigated (Appendix C). Furthermore, two test series with fir (Fi1, Fi2), one pine (Pi1) and one spruce (Sp1) from coniferous wood were investigated (Appendix D). A total of 83 samples were analysed. This systematic collection allows to compare the structural differences of conserved WAW (Wittköpper et al., 2016; Stelzner et al., 2021, 2022). Each test series in this study consists of samples derived from the same object or context (Appendix E). This selection ensures comparable samples of the same genus, excavation site, and state of preservation conserved by the different treatments. Due to the different sizes of the objects, the number of samples varied. Therefore, not all test series contain all conservation methods.

2.2. Micro-computed tomography

The μ CT measurements were performed on the in-house laboratory X-ray μ CT system (Diondo d2, Germany) of the Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts. An optimized setup and acquisition protocol for the μ CT measurements was developed for the conserved wood samples. For this purpose, the X-ray source (XWT-225 TCHE+ from X-RAY WorX, Garbsen, Germany) was switched to high power mode and an accelerating voltage of 120 kV and a filament current of 167 μ A with a 1 mm aluminum filter were selected. Wood samples were fixed in a sample holder and placed in the sample chamber. The specimen was rotated 360°, and X-ray images were acquired at each rotation step in

continuous rotation mode during acquisition. X-ray projections were acquired using a 4343 DX-1 X-ray detector (Varex, Salt Lake City, U.S.A.) with a pixel size of 139 μm . The distances between the X-ray source and the sample varied from 160 to 250 mm, depending on the sample size, and the distance between the X-ray source and the detector was 860 mm, resulting in a magnification between 3.4 and 5.4 and a nominal voxel size between 27 and 44 μm . A total of 3000 projection images were acquired per measurement during the 360° sample rotation. The resulting projections were converted into a 3D image stack of approximately 3000 \times 3000 \times 3000 voxels using CERA reconstruction software (Siemens Healthineers, Germany) based on the filtered back-projection Feldkamp algorithm (Feldkamp et al., 1984). The achieved resolution of the μCT measurements depends on the size of the samples (Stelzner and Million, 2015). Appendix B-D gives an overview of the samples, their size and the achieved resolution of the μCT measurements.

2.3. Tree ring width measurements

Tree ring widths were measured in the image cross-sections of the μCT data using VGStudio Max 3.4© software from Volume Graphics, Heidelberg, Germany. Two radii were measured for each sample. After the μCT measurements, the samples were prepared for conventional analogue manual measurements. For this purpose, the surface was levelled and polished with the aid of a geared eccentric sander (Festool, RO150FEQ). An ascending grit of 40, 80, 180, 400, and finally 800 was used to grind the sample surfaces. In a few cases, additional surface preparation with a conventional razor blade was required. Subsequently, also along two radii, the tree ring widths were measured with a stereo microscope on a linear measuring table (Rinntech LintabTM). Care was taken to ensure that the position of the radii matched as closely as possible the position of the radii measured in the μCT data. To validate the two measurements, the tree ring curves of each radius per specimen of the analog and μCT measurements were visually and statistically cross-dated by their degree of Gleichläufigkeit and their t-values (Baillie and Pilcher, 1973; Hollstein, 1980) (Fig. 1). In the next step, the number of rings of the analogue and μCT measurements were compared. In this way, it was checked whether all rings could be detected on the basis of μCT . To verify the agreement of the two measurement methods, the arithmetic mean of the tree ring widths was

determined. Therefore, the mean value of the tree ring widths measured analogously and with μCT was calculated for each sample. The difference of the determined mean value from the μCT to the analogue measurement was used as a measurement variable for the detection of deviations. The obtained deviation is thus an easy to compare and interpret measure of the accuracy of the agreement between the measurements. Furthermore, the root mean square error (RMSE) was calculated (Vannoppen et al., 2017) to provide a further estimation of the degree of agreement between the two methods. The data from this study (measured tree ring widths, μCT cross sections and the images of the cutting planes for the manual measurements) will be available on the project homepage (www.rgzm.de/cutaway).

2.4. Grey value analysis

In order to assess the influence of a conservation agent on the visibility of the rings in the μCT images, the quality of the data was evaluated by calculating the contrast. For this purpose, the data were calibrated during import into VGStudio MAX 3.4© by setting the background (air) and the most absorbing part of the wood (e.g. medullary ray) to specific grey values. The maximum and minimum grey value possible with 16-bit data sets is 65535 and 0, respectively. Within the possible 65535 grey values, the background (air) was set to the grey value 10000 and the material (wood) to the grey value 50000 when calibrating the measurements. In μCT data, grey value profiles were taken along the radii of the ring width measurements. The distances were equal for each test series and the profiles were taken without gaps or inclusions in the wood that might interfere with the result. The length of the profiles was adapted to the sample sizes: 100 mm for the second oak test series (Oa2) and the pine samples (Pi1), 80 mm for the beech (Be1), the first fir (Fi1) and the spruce (Sp1) samples, 50 mm for the first oak test series (Oa1) (Fig. 2), 40 mm for the ash samples (As1), 30 mm for the second fir test series (Fi2), 20 mm for the alder samples (Al1) and 10 mm for the third oak test series (Oa3). The values were exported and the image contrast C was calculated by dividing the difference of the maximum I_{\max} and minimum I_{\min} by the mean value $I_{\bar{x}}$ of the grey value profiles (Peli, 1990):

$$C = \frac{I_{\max} - I_{\min}}{I_{\bar{x}}}$$

Fig. 1. Measurement radii of tree ring widths, (a) analog on the prepared surface of the sample, (b) in the μCT data of the sample and (c) synchronous position of the tree ring curves of the measured radii from the different methods of the sample conserved with saccharose from the first oak test series in (Oa1-Sac).

Fig. 2. Grey value profile (100 mm) along one tree ring widths measurement radius in the calibrated μ CT data of the sample conserved with Kauramin 800® from the second oak test series (Oa2-K800).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Tree ring width measurements

3.1.1. Ring-porous wood

The sample of the first oak test series (Oa1-Air) dried without conservation illustrates the need for conservation. Fig. 3 clearly shows how

the highly degraded areas of the sample have completely collapsed in the outer region. In contrast to the conserved samples, the tree ring widths can no longer be measured here. Collapse here is along a boundary of high and low degraded wood and not along the boundary of heartwood and sapwood. The distinction between the differently preserved areas can be seen in the μ CT data for all conserved woods. In the sample conserved with Kauramin 800®, the heartwood and sapwood are also visible (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3. μ CT cross sections of the non-conserved sample from the first oak test series (Oa1-Air).

Fig. 4. Heartwood and sapwood in the sample conserved with Kauramin 800® of the first oak test series (Oa1-K800) (left) and μ CT cross section of this part (right).

The results of the ring width measurements show that in all conserved ring-porous wood samples the rings could be captured on the basis of μ CT data (Appendix F). The resolution of 19–44 μ m achieved in the various measurements made it possible to detect ring widths down to the smallest ring width of 0.18 mm, regardless of the conservation method used. Moreover, in some cases it was possible to detect some rings at the end of the radii better with μ CT than with the conventional measurement method. The reason for this is that the heavily degraded and partially deformed outer parts of the wood samples were in some cases better visible in the μ CT data than on the sample surface, which was partially smeared by the conservation agent. A similar preparation of the sample would in theory have been possible with the conventional cutting techniques. However, only CT enables the selection of the optimum cutting plane because with conventional techniques cut planes

cannot be reconsidered any more. In the μ CT data, the rings in these areas were more clearly visible in the axially slightly lower planes, i.e. the views below the surface within the wood (Figs. 5 and 6). To verify the accuracy of the tree ring width measurements in the cross sections of the μ CT data, the results were compared in terms of mean ring widths and the RMSE with the conventional measurements. Overall, the measurements in the μ CT data agreed well with the microscopic measurements (Fig. 7). The deviation for all samples in the first two test series of oak (Oa1 and Oa2) and the ash test series (As1) had minimum overall deviations of less than 0.1 mm (Fig. 7a). In terms of tree ring widths, this corresponds to a maximum deviation of about 5%. The RMSE values are mostly comparable to those found when CT- and conventional measurements of modern oak increment cores were compared (Vannoppen et al., 2017). The larger deviations above 0.1 mm in the third oak test

Fig. 5. Breaks and voids of the outer areas in the surface of the three step PEG conserved sample of the first oak test series (Oa1-PEG3) (left) and μ CT cross section of this part (right). Yellow triangle locates the radius of the conventional tree ring measurement.

Fig. 6. Degraded parts and smeared surface in the outer areas of the two step PEG conserved sample of the first oak test series (Oa1-PEG2) (left) and μ CT cross section of this part (right).

series (Oa3) can probably be explained by the more eccentric growth of the annual rings of the oak branch from which the samples were taken. This also explains the higher RMSE values in this sample series (Fig. 7b). Such irregular growth can be accurately quantified by the application of algorithms capable to recognise the entire tree-ring profiles, and thus, average ring width values computed over thousands of radial directions (Martinez-Garcia et al., 2021, 2022). The measured tree rings allowed to date the samples of the first oak test series (Oa1) to 86 CE (with waney edge) and the samples of the second oak test series (Oa2) to 115 BCE.

3.1.2. Diffuse-porous wood

Both air dried samples (Al1-Air and Be1-Air) of the diffuse-porous test series are strongly collapsed, which has led to the deformation of the tree rings (Fig. 8). In the alder samples (Al1), the bark of the branches can be seen in the μ CT data (Fig. 8). The annual rings in this series of samples are sometimes difficult to recognize in the μ CT data, in particular for samples conserved with lactitol/trehalose and silicon oil. Also, in the samples conserved with PEG, not all rings can be seen very well (Fig. 8). In this context, it is worth noting that tree ring measurements of many diffuse-porous woods, where the ring boundary is indistinct, are challenging even with the conventional analog tree-ring measurement. Chalk is often applied on the prepared surface to make tree ring boundaries more visible. Such a possibility does not exist when using μ CT. Nevertheless, in all the diffuse-porous samples (Al1 and Be1) all tree rings could be measured by μ CT and the tree ring widths of the beech samples (Be1) have mostly a good agreement with the analogous measurements (Appendix G, Fig. 7). The resolution of 27–35 μ m obtained in the various measurements was sufficient to detect ring widths down to the smallest ring width of 0.4 mm. Due to the poor state of preservation, the analogous measurement of the tree ring widths on the surface of the alder sample conserved with lactitol/trehalose (Al1-LaTr) was not possible. In axially lower levels below the surface, it was also possible to measure the annual rings here using μ CT. However, it has to

be taken into account that the test series with alder involves small samples with only four tree rings. It can be assumed that due to the small pore size and narrow density contrast in μ CT-data of diffuse-porous woods, measurements would be even more difficult for larger samples (Grabner et al., 2007, 2009). The deviations of the tree ring widths (Fig. 7) in the alder (Al1-Air) and beech (Be1-Air) samples can probably be explained by the deformations of the tree rings due to air drying. Overall, the rings of the alder samples (Al1) have grown more irregularly, which is also reflected in the values of the tree ring widths and the high RMSE values (Fig. 7).

3.1.3. Coniferous wood

The tree ring width measurements on the coniferous wood samples (Fi1, Fi2, Pi1 and Sp1) prove that all tree rings could be detected using the μ CT data (Appendix H). The voxel resolution of 32–45 μ m allowed ring widths down to the smallest ring width of 0.12 mm (3–4 voxels) to be measured in the μ CT data, regardless of the conservation method. Density variations in the tree rings are difficult to detect but can be followed and clarified by tracing the tree ring in the different slices of the μ CT data (Fig. 9). Furthermore, in some cases again some rings at the beginning or at the end of the radii could be detected better with μ CT than with the conventional measuring method, which again can be explained by the axially somewhat deeper planes below the surface in μ CT data in which further rings are visible at the outer sample area. This was particularly the case with the sample conserved with alcohol-ether-resin (Pi1-AIEt), where a larger part of the sample had broken off at the edge of the surface, which explains why 12 additional annual rings could be measured in an axially deeper layer on the basis of the μ CT (Fig. 10). The comparison of the averaged ring width measurements in the μ CT data with the analog measurements showed good agreement (Fig. 7). The deviation for all samples in the test series (Fi1, Fi2, Pi1 and Sp1) showed only minimal overall deviations of less than 0.1 mm and mostly good RMSE values.

Fig. 7. Difference between the arithmetic mean tree ring widths (a) and the RMSE (b) from μ CT to analog measurement.

3.2. Visibility of tree rings in μ CT data

3.2.1. Ring-porous wood

In the μ CT data of the ring-porous wood samples, the annual rings were overall well visible. However, differences were evident in the sample series themselves and in the different conservation agents. These differences were confirmed by the grey value profiles and the contrast calculated from the profiles (Fig. 11). Evident was the poorer contrast in the μ CT data of the ash (As1) and the third series of oak (Oa3) samples. The differences in the test objects themselves can be explained to some extent due to the condition of the wood (Appendix B). The more degraded samples from both the ash (As1) and the third oak (Oa3) test series have a lower contrast than the better preserved sample from the first and second oak test series (Oa1 and Oa2). Poorer contrast is also

seen in this two series of oak samples (Oa1 and Oa2), in particular in the more degraded outer areas of the samples. Another explanation for lower contrasts is that the third oak series (Oa3) is extracted from branches. Here, the pores of the early wood are less pronounced than those of the other two series of oak samples (Oa1 and Oa2), maybe due to the vessel tapering according to the widened pipe model (Koçillari et al., 2021). This effect declares a correlation between vessel area and plant height/leaf area and needs to be taken into account due to differences in conduit size within one botanical genus. In the ash samples (As1), the lower contrast in the μ CT data could also be explained by the fact that this species forms fewer large early wood pores in contrast to oak (Wagenführ, 1996).

When evaluating the different conservation methods, the first noticeable aspect is that all of them have an impact on the contrast in the

Fig. 8. Collapsed alder sample (A11-Air) without conservation (left) and alder sample conserved with two step PEG (A11-PEG2) with visible bark (right).

Fig. 9. Density variations in a tree ring of the pine sample conserved with Kauramin800® (Pi-K800) at the surface (left) and in the μ CT data (right).

μ CT data. Thus, a significant decrease in contrast can be observed for all conservation agents compared to the non-conserved samples. The highest contrast values resulted from measurements without conservation agent, followed by the samples conserved with alcohol-ether resin, Kauramine 800® and saccharose (Fig. 11). Lactitol/trehalose and the various PEG-treated samples and especially those treated with silicone oil showed the lowest values. The influence of the conservation is most evident in the third series of oak samples (Oa3), where, for example, a clear difference can be seen between the sample conserved with alcohol-ether resin (Oa3-A1Et) and the sample conserved with silicone oil (Oa3-Sil) (Fig. 12). An explanation could again lie in the less pronounced pores of the early wood of the branches in this test series, which could be filled by the silicone oil, thus reducing the contrast of the measurement.

3.2.2. Diffuse-porous wood

The tree rings were also visible and measurable in the μ CT data of the diffuse-porous woods examined here. However, in the case of the alder samples (A11), the separation was difficult in some cases. In contrast to the test series of the ring-porous woods, the non-conserved samples of the diffuse-porous woods did not have the highest contrast in the μ CT data (see Fig. 13), which can probably be explained by the strong collapse of the two samples (see Fig. 8). The varying influence of the conservation agent on the contrast in the μ CT data is also confirmed by the diffuse-porous woods. The methods with alcohol-ether-resin and Kauramin 800® have higher contrast values than saccharose, lactitol/trehalose, and the treatments with PEG. Silicone oil again has the lowest value.

The μ CT contrast is lower in the alder samples (A11) than in the beech samples (Be1) (Fig. 14), which beside of the different wood species, also

Fig. 10. Breaks and voids of the outer area in the surface of the alcohol-ether-resin conserved pine sample (Pi1-AIEt) (left) and μ CT cross section of this part (right).

Fig. 11. Difference of the mean contrast with standard deviation in the μ CT data calculated from the grey value profiles of the two radii of the tree ring measurements of the ring-porous wood ash (As1) and oak (Oa1, Oa2 and Oa3) samples.

may again be explained by the fact that they are from a smaller tree diameter with less pronounced pores than the beech samples from a stem (Koçillari et al., 2021; Schweingruber, 2001).

3.2.3. Coniferous wood

In the coniferous woods, the tree rings are well visible due to a high contrast of early and late wood of this wood species in the μ CT data. The non-conserved samples have the highest contrast, while among the conserved samples again the alcohol-ether-resin method followed by Kauramin 800® have the highest contrast values. Saccharose, lactitol/trehalose and the methods with PEG have again lower values and silicone oil display the lowest contrast value (cf. Fig. 15). The difference in the contrast of the different test series may be explained by the differing wood species and the preservation state of the samples. The second fir sample series (Fi2) with a lower contrast have poorer preservation states than the first fir test series (Fi1) (Appendix D). Furthermore, the different contrast of the two fir sample series could possibly be explained by the fact that the second fir sample series (Fi2) came from a pile with a

small diameter, and thus, from a younger tree with less pronounced early and late wood than the samples from the first fir sample series (Fi1) from a board (Fig. 16) (Schweingruber, 2001).

3.2.4. Mean contrast of all samples

Considering the averaged contrast in the μ CT data of all samples, the influence of the different conservation agents displays a clear trend (Fig. 17a). The alcohol-ether-resin method shows the best values overall. Calculated from the mean contrast values of all measurements, the alcohol-ether-resin method reduces the contrast by about 4% compared to the samples without conservation. It is followed by Kauramin800®, which decreases contrast by about 14%.

The third best contrast values with a lowering of 23% compared to the air dried samples are obtained by the method with saccharose, followed by the methods with PEG (contrast reduction PEG1: 34%, PEG2: 31% and PEG3: 29%) and lactitol/trehalose, which lowers the contrast 31%. Silicone oil caused lowest contrast, with a decrease of 45%. This can probably be explained by the fact that the methods using silicone oil,

Fig. 12. μ CT cross sections showing the differences in contrast of the samples from the third oak test series conserved with alcohol-ether-resin (Oa3-AIEt) (left) and silicone oil (Oa3-Sil) right.

Fig. 13. Difference of the mean contrast with standard deviation in the μ CT data calculated from the grey value profiles of the two radii of the tree ring measurements of the diffuse-porous wood alder (Al1) and beech (Be1) samples.

PEG, lactitol/trehalose and saccharose tend to fill the pores and thus also reduce the contrast the most. This observation would also explain that full impregnation of oak with PEG as described by [Bill et al. \(2012\)](#) prevents visualization of the rings using μ CT while conservation with PEG followed by freeze-drying still allows this as described here and by [Daly and Ebert \(2021\)](#). In the case of full impregnation with PEG followed by air drying, much more conservation agent is used ([Hoffmann, 1986](#)) which remains more in the wood cell structure than with the freeze-drying method ([Jensen et al., 2011](#)). In contrast, the rings of the maple wheel conserved with the same method (PEG and freeze-drying) by [Wiesner et al. \(2016\)](#) could not be visualized, which can be explained by the different wood species and the smaller pore size ([Grabner et al., 2009](#)).

The influence of the wood anatomy of the different wood species on the contrast is also evident from the averaged values of the contrast ([Fig. 17b](#)). There is a tendency for the coniferous woods (Fi1 and Pi1) to show the highest contrast, followed by the second oak test series (Oa2). The diffuse-porous alder (Al1) has the lowest value. Other factors such as the condition of the wood, the age of the tree, and which part of a tree

the sample came from also play a role, as can be seen in the oak (Oa1, Oa2 and Oa3) and fir (Fi1 and Fi2) samples.

4. Conclusion

Within this study, all tree rings of the conserved WAW samples from different wood species could be recognized and measured in the μ CT data. In two test series of oak samples (Oa1 and Oa2) it was possible to successfully cross-date them with reference chronologies. The achieved resolution in the μ CT data was sufficient to detect all tree rings down to the smallest tree ring width of 0.12 mm. The accuracy of the method could be confirmed by the comparison with conventional measurements. Furthermore, in some cases it was possible to obtain more rings in the samples with μ CT than with conventional microscopy due to the three-dimensionality of the data.

Even though the annual rings could all be measured, the different influence of the investigated conservation agents on the quality of the μ CT data became clear. The alcohol-ether-resin method followed by Kauramin800® obtained the best results. However, a decrease in the

Fig. 14. μ CT cross sections of the alder sample (Al1-Sac) (left) and the beech sample (Be1-Sac) (right) conserved with saccharose.

Fig. 15. Difference of the mean contrast with standard deviation in the μ CT data calculated from the grey value profiles of the two radii of the tree ring measurements of the coniferous wood fir (Fi1 and Fi2), pine (Pi1) and spruce (Sp1) samples.

Fig. 16. μ CT cross sections of the sample from the first fir test series (Fi1-PEG2) (left) and the sample from the second fir test series (Fi2-PEG) (right) conserved with the two step PEG method.

Fig. 17. Mean contrast with standard deviation in μ CT for the different conservation methods (a) and the different wood species (b), calculated from the grey value profiles of the tree ring measurements of all samples.

contrast in the μ CT data was detectable for all conservation agents compared to the non-conserved samples. This seems to be especially the case for the conservation methods with silicone oil, lactitol/trehalose, PEG and saccharose, which have the property to fill the pores of the woods (Stelzner et al., 2023).

It was also shown that the condition of the wood has a direct influence on the visibility of the tree rings in the μ CT data. Thus, the contrast in the measurements of the poorly preserved wood is lower than in the well-preserved wood. The visibility of the rings in the μ CT data here is also dependent on the pore size and the expression of early and late wood, which depends on various factors such as the tree species, the age of the tree, the position of the wood in the tree, etc.

In this context, however, it should be mentioned that WAW is a very heterogeneous material with many different states of preservation and this study is limited to 10 objects. Consequently, it would be desirable to verify the results on more objects.

Overall, the experiments confirm, though, that μ CT is a powerful and accurate tool for dendrochronology of conserved WAW. Successful measurements of tree ring widths depend on the quality of the μ CT data. In addition to the resolution of a measurement, the contrast is also decisive for the visibility of the annual rings. However, other factors must be considered to obtain sufficiently good μ CT data. In addition to the equipment used (Bill et al., 2012; Krivánková et al., 2018; Mori et al., 2020), these are in particular the wood species and the diameter of the object under investigation (Grabner et al., 2007, 2009; Stelzner and

Million, 2015). In addition to these criteria, this study has shown that for successful dating of conserved WAW finds using μ CT, the condition of the wood and the applied conservation method are also crucial factors.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Overview of conservation methods

Conservation method	Institution	Treatment	Impregnation solution	Number of samples
Alcohol-ether-resin (Alet)	Schweizerisches Nationalmuseum, Zürich, Switzerland	Exchange of water with ethanol. Exchange of ethanol with diethyl ether. Soaking of wood with diethyl ether in resin-diethyl solution. Drying by evaporation of the diethyl ether in the vacuum vessel. Application of surface protection 3% Paraloid B72 solution in acetone.	70.7% diethyl ether, 16.1% dammar resin, 6.4% rosin, 3.2% dienol D102, 3.2% rhizinus oil, 0.4% PEG 400	8 (alder, ash, beech, fir (2), oak (2), pine)
Kauramin 800® (K800)	Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie, Mainz, Germany	Bath impregnation at room temperature. Replacement of the solution when early polymerisation occurs. Curing of the impregnated wood in the heating cabinet at 60 °C. Afterwards slow, controlled air-drying. Dip in linseed oil varnish. Starting with 30% concentration. Increasing monthly in 10% steps up to 70%. Bath temperature 55 °C. After removal from the bath, the surfaces were dusted with crystalline lactitol monohydrate and dried in a heating oven over a period of one week. After drying, the surface was cleaned by dabbing with damp cloths.	25% Kauramin 800® solution (72 L resin + 210 L deionised water, 3.6 L urea, 7.2 L triethylene glycol)	10 (alder, ash, beech, fir (2), oak (3), pine, spruce)
Lactitol- trehalose (LaTr)	Brandenburgisches Landesamt für Denkmalpflege, Zossen, Germany	Starting with 30% concentration. Increasing monthly in 10% steps up to 70%. Bath temperature 55 °C. After removal from the bath, the surfaces were dusted with crystalline lactitol monohydrate and dried in a heating oven over a period of one week. After drying, the surface was cleaned by dabbing with damp cloths.	Lactitol-trehalose solution (9:1) 30–70%. Addition of biocide if necessary (0,1% Bioban 404)	7 (alder, beech, fir, oak (2), pine, spruce)
Polyethylene glycol (PEG 2000) one-step and freeze-drying (PEG1)	Nationalmuseet, Copenhagen, Denmark	Starting with 10% PEG 2000 solution. Increasing the concentration up to 40% at room temperature. Freeze-drying in cooled chamber (approx. –30 °C). Removal of excess PEG from the surface with a soft brush and ethanol. Subsequent surface stabilisation with 25% PEG 2000 solution in ethanol.	PEG 2000, 10 – 40% solution with tap water	10 (alder, ash, beech, fir (2), oak (3), pine, spruce)
Polyethylene glycol (PEG 400 and 4000) two-step and freeze-drying (PEG2)	Brandenburgisches Landesamt für Denkmalpflege, Zossen, Germany	Soaking in demineralised water. Starting with 5% PEG 400 solution. Raising the concentration in 5% steps. At its calculated final concentration, it was kept constant. Then the increase of PEG 4000 solution was continued in 5% steps up to its final concentration. Precooling of the wood to 5 °C then deep-freezing to – 25 to – 35 °C, freeze-drying in cooled chamber (approx. –30 °C).	PEG-solution in demineralised water (PEG 400 and PEG 4000) was adapted according to the condition of the wood (PEGcon)	10 (alder, ash, beech, fir (2), oak (3), pine, spruce)
Polyethylene glycol (PEG 400, 1500 and 4000) three-step and freeze-drying (PEG3)	Archäologische Staatssammlung, Munich, Germany	Soaking in demineralised water. Starting with 11% increasing to 15% PEG 400 solution at room temperature. 16% increasing to 20.5% PEG 1500 solution at 40 °C. 20.5% increasing to 27.5% PEG 4000 solution at 40 °C. Washing of the wood and wrapping in cellulose tissues. Intermediate storage in freezer (–25 to –35 °C) until freeze-drying. Subsequent freeze-drying in a cooled chamber (approx. –30 °C). Excess of PEG was removed with a brush and ethanol.	PEG-solution in demineralised water: 15% PEG 400, 20.5% PEG 1500, 27.5% PEG 4000	10 (alder, ash, beech, fir (2), oak (3), pine, spruce)
Saccharose (Sac)	Sächsische Landesamt für Archäologie, Dresden, Germany	Concentrated the solution in 10% steps, from 10% up to 60% sugar solution at room temperature. Slow, controlled air-drying in microperforated bags. Removal of crystallised sugar residues from the surface with damp sponge.	Aqueous saccharose solution 10–60%. If necessary biocide addition composed of 0.6%, sodium benzoate (E211), 0.5% Parmetol K40, 0.5% Quartasept Plus and 0.02% Tallofin OT	10 (alder, ash, beech, fir (2), oak (3), pine, spruce)
Silicone oil (Sil)	Texas University, Texas, USA	Exchange of water with ethanol. Exchange of ethanol with acetone. Placing the still dripping wet acetone-impregnated samples in impregnation solution under normal atmospheric conditions. Triggering the polymerisation of the impregnation solution by gaseous catalyst: DBTDA (dibutyl diacetate).	80% silicone oil (SFD1 (66%) + SFD5 (34%) - silanol functional polydimethylsiloxanes "PDMS") and 20% crosslinker MTMS (methyltrimethoxysilane)	8 (alder, ash, beech, fir (2), oak (2), pine)

Appendix B. Conservation, condition, dimensions and μ CT resolution of the ring-porous wood samples

Sample	KUR-No.	Genus	Conservation method	Umax (%)	Basic density (g/cm ³)	Dimensions L, Ø (cm)	Resolution μ CT (μ m)
As1-Air	V28-27	Ash	Air dried	738	0.124	11, 12	43
As1-AIEt	V28-23	Ash	Alcohol-Ether	994	0.094	11, 12	44
As1-K800	V28-30	Ash	Kauramin 800®	961	0.097	11, 12	35
As1-PEG1	V28-08	Ash	PEG (1)	1291	0.074	11, 12	35
As1-PEG2	V28-10	Ash	PEG (2)	1195	0.079	11, 12	35
As1-PEG3	V28-36	Ash	PEG (3)	929	0.100	11, 12	44
As1-Sac	V28-07	Ash	Saccharose	1376	0.069	11, 12	35
As1-Sil	V28-24	Ash	Silicone oil	983	0.095	11, 12	35
Oa1-Air	V10-02	Oak	Air dried	201	0.374	17, 7	32
Oa1-K800	V10-06	Oak	Kauramin 800®	198	0.378	16, 7	32
Oa1-LaTr	V10-33	Oak	Lactitol/trehalose	160	0.441	15, 7	32
Oa1-PEG1	V10-29	Oak	PEG (1)	179	0.407	11, 7	32
Oa1-PEG2	V10-31	Oak	PEG (2)	176	0.412	12, 7	32
Oa1-PEG3	V10-39	Oak	PEG (3)	181	0.404	13, 7	32
Oa1-Sac	V10-03	Oak	Saccharose	163	0.435	14, 7	32
Oa2-Air	V16-15	Oak	Air dried	362	0.233	12, 16	33
Oa2-AIEt	V16-09	Oak	Alcohol-Ether	175	0.414	12, 16	32
Oa2-K800	V16-25	Oak	Kauramin 800®	228	0.339	12, 16	44
Oa2-PEG1	V16-18	Oak	PEG (1)	189	0.391	12, 16	35
Oa2-PEG2	V16-32	Oak	PEG (2)	237	0.329	12, 16	44
Oa2-PEG3	V16-36	Oak	PEG (3)	188	0.393	12, 16	35
Oa2-Sac	V16-17	Oak	Saccharose	184	0.399	12, 16	35
Oa2-Sil	V16-13	Oak	Silicone oil	187	0.394	12, 16	32
Oa3-Air	V27-17	Oak	Air dried	577	0.155	12-14, 5-6	19
Oa3-AIEt	V27-40	Oak	Alcohol-Ether	527	0.168	12-14, 5-6	32
Oa3-K800	V27-07	Oak	Kauramin 800®	646	0.140	12-14, 5-6	26
Oa3-LaTr	V27-30	Oak	Lactitol/trehalose	566	0.158	12-14, 5-6	26
Oa3-PEG1	V27-12	Oak	PEG (1)	691	0.132	12-14, 5-6	32
Oa3-PEG2	V27-02	Oak	PEG (2)	578	0.155	12-14, 5-6	32
Oa3-PEG3	V27-01	Oak	PEG (3)	557	0.160	12-14, 5-6	39
Oa3-Sac	V27-21	Oak	Saccharose	434	0.200	12-14, 5-6	26
Oa3-Sil	V27-10	Oak	Silicone oil	520	0.170	12-14, 5-6	26

Appendix C. Conservation, condition, dimensions and μ CT resolution of the diffuse-porous wood samples

Sample	KUR-No.	Genus	Conservation Method	Umax (%)	Basic Density (G/Cm ³)	Dimensions L, Ø (CM)	Resolution μ CT (μ m)
Al1-Air	v24-23	Alder	Air Dried	743	0.124	20, 3-5	27
Al1-AIEt	V24-45	Alder	Alcohol-Ether	706	0.129	12, 3-5	27
Al1-K800	V24-60	Alder	Kauramin 800®	958	0.098	16, 3-5	30
Al1-LaTr	V24-19	Alder	Lactitol/Trehalose	891	0.104	14, 3-5	30
Al1-PEG1	V24-13	Alder	PEG (1)	853	0.109	17, 3-5	35
Al1-PEG2	V24-63	Alder	PEG (2)	671	0.136	18, 3-5	27
Al1-PEG3	V24-21	Alder	PEG (3)	1048	0.090	19, 3-5	30
Al1-Sac	V24-34	Alder	Saccharose	820	0.113	13, 3-5	27
Al1-Sil	V24-56	Alder	Silicone Oil	807	0.114	15, 3-5	30
Be1-Air	V07-23	Beech	Air Dried	664	0.137	20, 9	35
Be1-AIEt	V07-18	Beech	Alcohol-Ether	735	0.125	12, 9	35
Be1-K800	V07-14	Beech	Kauramin 800®	720	0.127	19, 9	35
Be1-LaTr	V07-Exp3	Beech	Lactitol/Trehalose	566	0.158	17, 9	35
Be1-PEG1	V07-09	Beech	PEG (1)	772	0.119	13, 9	35
Be1-PEG2	V07-27	Beech	PEG (2)	654	0.139	14, 9	35
Be1-PEG3	V07-08	Beech	PEG (3)	747	0.123	15, 9	35
Be1-Sac	V07-01	Beech	Saccharose	748	0.123	16, 9	35
Be1-Sil	V07-37	Beech	Silicone Oil	808	0.114	18, 9	35

Appendix D. Conservation, condition (¹ Mean value of the sample series), dimensions and μ CT resolution of the coniferous wood samples

Sample	KUR-No.	Genus	Conservation method	Umax (%)	Basic density (g/cm ³)	Dimensions L, Ø (cm)	Resolution μ CT (μ m)
Fi1-Air	V22-28	Fir	Air dried	381	0.223	30, 9	32
Fi1-AIEt	V22-09	Fir	Alcohol-Ether	398	0.215	22, 9	32
Fi1-K800	V22-33	Fir	Kauramin 800®	487	0.181	26, 9	32
Fi1-LaTr	V22-26	Fir	Lactitol/trehalose	352	0.239	24, 9	32
Fi1-PEG1	V22-22	Fir	PEG (1)	432	0.201	27, 9	32

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Sample	KUR-No.	Genus	Conservation method	Umax (%)	Basic density (g/cm ³)	Dimensions L, Ø (cm)	Resolution µCT (µm)
Fi1-PEG2	V22-31	Fir	PEG (2)	371 ¹	0.228 ¹	28, 9	32
Fi1-PEG3	V22-35	Fir	PEG (3)	241	0.325	29, 9	32
Fi1-Sac	V22-11	Fir	Saccharose	285	0.284	23, 9	32
Fi1-Sil	V22-05	Fir	Silicone oil	333	0.250	25, 9	32
Fi2-Air	V30-Exp1	Fir	Air dried	465	0.188	11, 6-7	40
Fi2-AIEt	V30-33	Fir	Alcohol-Ether	695	0.131	11, 6-7	40
Fi2-K800	V30-09	Fir	Kauramin 800®	601	0.150	11, 6-7	40
Fi2-PEG1	V30-04	Fir	PEG (1)	542	0.164	11, 6-7	40
Fi2-PEG2	V30-18	Fir	PEG (2)	632	0.143	11, 6-7	40
Fi2-PEG3	V30-15	Fir	PEG (3)	554	0.161	11, 6-7	40
Fi2-Sac	V30-17	Fir	Saccharose	599	0.150	11, 6-7	40
Fi2-Sil	V30-24	Fir	Silicone oil	548	0.163	11, 6-7	40
Pi1-Air	V03-01	Pine	Air dried	390	0.219	20, 9-12	39
Pi1-AIEt	V03-17	Pine	Alcohol-Ether	332 ¹	0.251 ¹	12, 9-12	40
Pi1-K800	V03-41	Pine	Kauramin 800®	332 ¹	0.251 ¹	19, 9-12	40
Pi1-LaTr	V03-28	Pine	Lactitol/trehalose	332 ¹	0.251 ¹	17, 9-12	40
Pi1-PEG1	V03-35	Pine	PEG (1)	332 ¹	0.251 ¹	13, 9-12	40
Pi1-PEG2	V03-32	Pine	PEG (2)	332 ¹	0.251 ¹	14, 9-12	40
Pi1-PEG3	V03-20	Pine	PEG (3)	332 ¹	0.251 ¹	15, 9-12	40
Pi1-Sac	V03-45	Pine	Saccharose	332 ¹	0.251 ¹	16, 9-12	40
Pi1-Sil	V03-42	Pine	Silicone oil	332 ¹	0.251 ¹	18, 9-12	40
Sp1-Air	V23-20	Spruce	Air dried	503	0.176	21, 10	40
Sp1-K800	V23-08	Spruce	Kauramin 800®	482	0.182	20, 10	40
Sp1-LaTr	V23-02	Spruce	Lactitol/trehalose	454	0.192	19, 10	40
Sp1-PEG1	V23-25	Spruce	PEG (1)	427	0.203	15, 10	40
Sp1-PEG2	V23-30	Spruce	PEG (2)	280	0.288	16, 10	40
Sp1-PEG3	V23-28	Spruce	PEG (3)	282	0.287	17, 10	40
Sp1-Sac	V23-29	Spruce	Saccharose	374	0.227	18, 10	40

Appendix E. Overview of the analysed WAW objects

Object No.	KUR-No.	Genus	Object	Period	Provenance
A11	V24	Alder (<i>Alnus</i>)	Stake	Roman	Jemgum, Leer, Germany
As1	V28	Ash (<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i>)	Pile	Neolithic	Arbon, Thurgau, Switzerland
Be1	V07	Beech (<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>)	Stem	Unknown	Glienke, Friedland, Germany
Fi1	V22	Fir (<i>Abies alba</i>)	Board	Roman	Cologne, Germany
Fi2	V30	Fir (<i>Abies alba</i>)	Pile	Neolithic	Arbon, Thurgau, Switzerland
Oa1	V10	Oak (<i>Quercus</i>)	Pile	Roman	Bad Nauheim, Germany
Oa2	V16	Oak (<i>Quercus</i>)	Plank	Roman	Bad Nauheim, Germany
Oa3	V27	Oak (<i>Quercus</i>)	Branch	Roman	Bad Nauheim, Germany
Pi1	V03	Pine (<i>Pinus</i>)	Waterpipe	Unknown	Stralsund, Germany
Sp1	V23	Spruce (<i>Picea abies</i>)	Beam	Roman	Cologne, Germany

Appendix F. Tree ring width measurements of the ring-porous wood samples

Sample	KUR-No.	Number of rings on surface	Number of rings µCT	Difference of rings	Difference in mean ring width (mm)	RMSE (mm)	Smallest ring width (mm)
As1-Air	V28-27	26	26	0	- 0.098	0.33	0.12
As1-AIEt	V28-23	26	26	0	- 0.048	0.26	0.40
As1-K800	V28-30	26	26	0	- 0.010	0.19	0.30
As1-PEG1	V28-08	48	48	0	- 0.005	0.16	0.41
As1-PEG2	V28-10	51	51	0	- 0.044	0.14	0.19
As1-PEG3	V28-36	48	48	0	+ 0.036	0.26	0.18
As1-Sac	V28-07	48	48	0	+ 0.035	0.27	0.30
As1-Sil	V28-24	25	25	0	+ 0.017	0.25	0.43
Oa1-Air	V10-02	37	37	0	- 0.022	0.29	0.32
Oa1-K800	V10-06	80	80	0	- 0.018	0.18	0.18
Oa1-LaTr	V10-33	59	64	+ 5 (µCT)	- 0.057	0.15	0.33
Oa1-PEG1	V10-29	79	82	+ 3 (µCT)	+ 0.004	0.17	0.20
Oa1-PEG2	V10-31	75	81	+ 6 (µCT)	+ 0.036	0.14	0.18
Oa1-PEG3	V10-39	80	82	+ 2 (µCT)	- 0.034	0.22	0.20
Oa1-Sac	V10-03	77	77	0	- 0.011	0.09	0.18
Oa2-Air	V16-15	50	51	+ 1 (µCT)	+ 0.076	0.23	0.91
Oa2-AIEt	V16-09	69	69	0	+ 0.016	0.17	1.05
Oa2-K800	V16-25	121	121	0	+ 0.008	0.16	0.59
Oa2-PEG1	V16-18	99	99	0	+ 0.003	0.32	0.64

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Sample	KUR-No.	Number of rings on surface	Number of rings μ CT	Difference of rings	Difference in mean ring width (mm)	RMSE (mm)	Smallest ring width (mm)
Oa2-PEG2	V16-32	120	120	0	+ 0.002	0.14	0.50
Oa2-PEG3	V16-36	101	101	0	+ 0.022	0.11	0.79
Oa2-Sac	V16-17	95	95	0	- 0.032	0.23	0.77
Oa2-Sil	V16-13	50	50	0	- 0.010	0.29	1.34
Oa3-Air	V27-17	10	10	0	+ 0.037	0.25	0.46
Oa3-AIEt	V27-40	10	10	0	+ 0.126	0.46	0.87
Oa3-K800	V27-07	12	12	0	- 0.151	0.35	0.47
Oa3-LaTr	V27-30	6	6	0	- 0.010	0.34	1.76
Oa3-PEG1	V27-12	15	15	0	- 0.087	0.33	0.45
Oa3-PEG2	V27-02	15	15	0	- 0.020	0.18	0.56
Oa3-PEG3	V27-01	15	15	0	- 0.030	0.22	0.72
Oa3-Sac	V27-21	14	14	0	+ 0.037	0.20	0.69
Oa3-Sil	V27-10	10	10	0	- 0.018	0.40	1.18

Appendix G. Tree ring width measurements of the diffuse-porous wood samples

Sample	KUR-No.	Number of rings on surface	Number of rings μ CT	Difference of rings	Difference in mean ring width (mm)	RMSE (mm)	Smallest ring width (mm)
Al1-Air	V24-23	4	4	0	- 0.110	1.14	1.19
Al1-AIEt	V24-45	7	7	0	- 0.221	0.76	0.40
Al1-K800	V24-60	8	8	0	+ 0.437	0.78	0.78
Al1-LaTr	V24-19	0	5	+ 5 (μ CT)			1.31
Al1-PEG1	V24-13	10	10	0	+ 0.012	0.58	0.58
Al1-PEG2	V24-63	5	5	0	- 0.064	0.65	0.96
Al1-PEG3	V24-21	7	7	0	+ 0.151	0.68	0.69
Al1-Sac	V24-34	5	5	0	+ 0.154	0.65	1.21
Al1-Sil	V24-56	5	5	0	+ 0.366	0.94	1.13
Be1-Air	V07-23	20	20	0	+ 0.232	0.40	0.74
Be1-AIEt	V07-18	26	26	0	+ 0.043	0.16	0.71
Be1-K800	V07-14	29	29	0	+ 0.016	0.18	0.54
Be1-LaTr	V07-Exp3	36	36	0	+ 0.028	0.37	0.77
Be1-PEG1	V07-09	24	24	0	+ 0.028	0.30	0.76
Be1-PEG2	V07-27	32	32	0	+ 0.025	0.31	0.44
Be1-PEG3	V07-08	26	26	0	- 0.051	0.46	0.95
Be1-Sac	V07-01	25	25	0	- 0.023	0.25	0.95
Be1-Sil	V07-37	28	28	0	+ 0.133	0.46	0.73

Appendix H. Tree ring width measurements of the coniferous wood samples

Sample	KUR-No.	Number of rings on surface	Number of rings μ CT	Difference of rings	Difference in mean ring width (mm)	RMSE (mm)	Smallest ring width (mm)
Fi1-Air	V22-28	35	36	+ 1 (μ CT)	+ 0.067	0.35	1.14
Fi1-AIEt	V22-09	31	32	+ 1 (μ CT)	- 0.012	0.16	1.56
Fi1-K800	V22-33	27	27	0	- 0.072	0.14	0.50
Fi1-LaTr	V22-26	23	23	0	- 0.027	0.12	0.59
Fi1-PEG1	V22-22	42	42	0	+ 0.017	0.16	0.52
Fi1-PEG2	V22-31	43	43	0	+ 0.039	0.18	0.58
Fi1-PEG3	V22-35	39	39	0	+ 0.038	0.13	0.44
Fi1-Sac	V22-11	31	31	0	- 0.033	0.21	1.85
Fi1-Sil	V22-05	34	34	0	+ 0.037	0.13	1.33
Fi2-Air	V30-Exp1	31	31	0	- 0.064	0.16	0.19
Fi2-AIEt	V30-33	16	16	0	- 0.014	0.11	0.36
Fi2-K800	V30-09	14	14	0	- 0.015	0.33	0.18
Fi2-PEG1	V30-04	32	32	0	- 0.014	0.11	0.12
Fi2-PEG2	V30-18	10	10	0	+ 0.048	0.18	0.57
Fi2-PEG3	V30-15	12	12	0	+ 0.043	0.25	0.45
Fi2-Sac	V30-17	10	10	0	- 0.001	0.27	1.37
Fi2-Sil	V30-24	38	38	0	+ 0.011	0.10	0.25
Pi1-Air	V03-01	71	72	+ 1 (μ CT)	+ 0.003	0.21	0.44
Pi1-AIEt	V03-17	59	71	+ 12 (μ CT)	+ 0.064	0.23	0.39
Pi1-K800	V03-41	40	40	0	- 0.039	0.40	0.26
Pi1-LaTr	V03-28	72	73	+ 1 (μ CT)	+ 0.021	0.23	0.41
Pi1-PEG1	V03-35	80	80	0	- 0.059	0.18	0.34

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Sample	KUR-No.	Number of rings on surface	Number of rings μ CT	Difference of rings	Difference in mean ring width (mm)	RMSE (mm)	Smallest ring width (mm)
Pi1-PEG2	V03-32	67	67	0	- 0.077	0.45	0.41
Pi1-PEG3	V03-20	64	65	+ 1 (μ CT)	+ 0.020	0.17	0.43
Pi1-Sac	V03-45	50	50	0	- 0.004	0.23	0.94
Pi1-Sil	V03-42	75	75	0	+ 0.003	0.18	0.34
Sp1-Air	V23-20	42	42	0	+ 0.072	0.53	0.73
Sp1-K800	V23-08	43	43	0	+ 0.037	0.33	1.05
Sp1-LaTr	V23-02	41	44	+ 3 (μ CT)	+ 0.083	0.32	1.07
Sp1-PEG1	V23-25	51	53	+ 2 (μ CT)	- 0.083	0.25	0.92
Sp1-PEG2	V23-30	54	54	0	- 0.051	0.27	1.05
Sp1-PEG3	V23-28	51	52	+ 1 (μ CT)	+ 0.022	0.28	0.30
Sp1-Sac	V23-29	54	55	+ 1 (μ CT)	+ 0.033	0.38	0.80

References

- Baillie, M., 2002. Future of dendrochronology with respect to archaeology. *Dendrochronologia* 20, 69–85.
- Baillie, M.G.L., Pilcher, J.R., 1973. A simple crossdating program for tree-ring research. *Tree-Ring Bull.* 33, 7–14.
- Belz, E., Brem, H., Hasenfratz, A., Kauermann, R., Leuzinger, U., Müller, C., Schweichel, R., Steiner, D., 2008. Neue Erkenntnisse zur Datierung der Holzstatue von Eschenz. *Jahrb. Archäol. Schweiz* 91, 134–140.
- Bill, J., Dalen, K.S., Daly, A., Johnsen, Ø., 2012. DendroCT – Dendrochronology without damage. *Dendrochronologia* 30, 223–230.
- Billamboz, A., 2014. Regional patterns of settlement and woodland developments: dendroarchaeology in the Neolithic pile-dwellings on Lake Constance (Germany). *Holocene* 24, 1278–1287.
- Bossemma, F.G., Domínguez-Delmás, M., Palenstijn, W.J., Kostenko, A., Dorscheid, J., Coban, S.B., Batenburg, K.J., 2021. A novel method for dendrochronology of large historical wooden objects using line trajectory X-ray tomography. *Sci. Rep.* 11, 1–12.
- Bräker, O.U., 2002. Measuring and data processing in tree-ring research – a methodological introduction. *Dendrochronologia* 20, 203–216.
- Bräker, O.U., Bill, J., Mühlenthaler, B., Schoch, W., Schweingruber, F.H., Haas, A., Hug, B., Kramer, W., Elmer, J.T., Tassigny, C.D., 1979. Zum derzeitigen Stand der Nassholzkonservierung. Diskussion der Grundlagen und Resultate eines von Fachlaboratorien 1976–1978 durchgeführten Methodenvergleiches. *Z. Für Schweiz. Archaeol. Kunstgesch.* 36, 97–145.
- Broda, M., Hill, C.A.S., 2021. Conservation of waterlogged wood—past, present and future perspectives. *Forests* 12, 1193.
- Christensen, M., Kutzke, H., Hansen, F.K., 2012. New materials used for the consolidation of archaeological wood—past attempts, present struggles, and future requirements. *J Cult Herit.* 13, 183–190.
- Cook, C., Grattan, D.A., 1990. method of calculation the concentration of PEG for freeze-drying waterlogged wood. In: Hoffmann, P. (Ed.), *Proceedings of the 4th ICOM-CC Group on Wet Organic Archaeological Materials Conference*, Bremerhaven, 1987. ICOM-CC, Bremerhaven, pp. 239–252.
- Daly, A., Streeton, N.L., 2017. Non-invasive dendrochronology of late-medieval objects in Oslo: refinement of a technique and discoveries. *Appl. Phys. A* 123 (6), 1–12.
- Daly, A., Ebert, B., 2021. Non-invasive dendrochronology – Pushing the boundaries of the technique. In: Bridgland, J. (Ed.), *Transcending boundaries: integrated approaches to conservation. ICOM-CC 19th Triennial Conference preprints*, Beijing, 2021. ICOM-CC, Paris, pp. 1–11.
- Domínguez-Delmás, M., Bossemma, F.G., Dorscheid, J., Coban, S.B., Hall-Aquitania, M., Batenburg, K.J., Hermens, E., 2021. X-ray computed tomography for non-invasive dendrochronology reveals a concealed double panelling on a painting from Rubens' studio. *PLoS One* 16, e0255792.
- Feldkamp, L.A., Davis, L.C., Kress, J.W., 1984. Practical cone-beam algorithm. *J. Opt. Soc. Am. A* 1, 612–619.
- Grabner, M., Salaberger, D., Okochi, T., 2009. The Need of High Resolution μ -X-ray CT in Dendrochronology and in Wood Identification. In: *Proceedings of the 6th International Symposium on Image and Signal Processing and Analysis. IEEE*, pp. 349–352.
- Grabner, M., Kastner, J., Klein, A., Reschreiter, J., Salaberger, D., 2007. Dendrochronologische Datierung von Holzfunden aus Hallstatt mit Hilfe der Röntgen-Computertomographie. In: Karl, R., Leskovar, J. (Eds.), *Interpretierte Eisenzeiten 2. Fallstudien, Methoden, Theorien. Studien zur Kulturgeschichte von Oberösterreich*, 19, pp. 99–108.
- Hanecca, K., Čufar, K., Beeckman, H., 2009. Oaks, tree-rings and wooden cultural heritage: a review of the main characteristics and applications of oak dendrochronology in Europe. *J. Archaeol. Sci.* 36, 1–11.
- Hoffmann, P., 1986. On the stabilization of waterlogged oakwood with PEG. II. Des. a two-step Treat. *multiquality Timbers Stud. Conserv.* 31, 103–113.
- Hollstein, E., 1980. *Mitteuropäische eichenchronologie*. Trier. *Grab. Forsch.* 11, 1–273.
- Hughes, M.K., 2002. Dendrochronology in climatology – the state of the art. *Dendrochronologia* 20, 95–116.
- Imazu, S., Morgós, A., 2002. An improvement on the Lactitol MC conservation method used for the conservation of archaeological waterlogged wood (The conservation method using Lactitol MC and Trehalose mixture). In: Hoffmann, P., Spriggs, J.A., Grant, T., Cook, C., Recht, A. (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 8th ICOM-CC Group on Wet Organic Archaeological Materials Conference*, Stockholm, 2001. ICOM-CC, Bremerhaven, pp. 413–428.
- Jensen, P., Petersen, A.H., Straetkvern, K., 2011. From the Skuldelev to the Roskilde ships - 50 years of shipwreck conservation at the National Museum of Denmark. In: Ek, M. (Ed.), *Shipwrecks 2011, Proceedings, Chemistry and Preservation of Waterlogged Wooden Shipwrecks*, Stockholm, 2011. Royal Institute of Technology, Stockholm, pp. 14–20.
- Kastner, J., Salaberger, D., Grabner, M., Mehofer, M., 2007. Mikro-Röntgencomputertomographie: Eine zerstörungsfreie Methode für die Archäologie. *Archäol. Österreichs* 18, 60–64.
- Keefer, E., Pfeifer-Schäller, I., Sauerwein, C., Wälischmiller, H., 2006. Voxel and STL-Data in Service of Archaeology – Digital Celts. In: Völker, J., Link, R. (Eds.), *EC NDT*. Berlin, Tu.3.2.4.
- Koçillari, L., Olson, M.E., Suweis, S., Rocha, R.P., Lovison, A., Cardin, F., Dawson, T.E., Echeverría, A., Fajardo, A., Lechthaler, S., Martínez-Pérez, C., Marcati, C.R., Kuo-Fang Chung, K.-F., Rosell, J.A., Segovia-Rivas, A., Williams, C.B., Petrone-Mendoza, E., Rinaldo, A., Anfodillo, T., Jayanth, R., Banavar, J.R., Marita, A., 2021. The Widened Pipe Model of plant hydraulic evolution. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 118, e2100314118.
- Křivánková, S., Nasswetrová, A., Šmíra, P., 2018. Comparison of image quality between a medical and an industrial CT scanner for use in non-destructive testing of tree-ring widths in an oak (*Quercus robur*) historical sculpture of Madonna. *Wood Res* 63, 155–165.
- Kuniholm, P., 2001. Dendrochronology and other applications of tree-ring studies in archaeology. In: Brothwell, D.R., Pollard, A.M. (Eds.), *The Handbook of Archaeological Sciences*. John Wiley & Sons, Hoboken, pp. 35–46.
- Maes, S.L., Vannoppen, A., Altman, J., Van den Bulcke, J., Decocq, G., De Mil, T., Depauw, L., Landuyt, D., Perring, M.P., Van Acker, J., Vanhellemont, M., 2017. Evaluating the robustness of three ring-width measurement methods for growth release reconstruction. *Dendrochronologia* 46, 67–76.
- Martínez-García, J., Stelzner, I., Stelzner, J., Gwerder, D., Schuetz, P., 2021. Automated 3D tree-ring detection and measurement from x-ray computed tomography. *Dendrochronologia* 69, 125877.
- Martínez-García, J., Stelzner, I., Stelzner, J., Gwerder, D., Million, S., Nelle, O., Schuetz, P., 2022. Curvilinear-tree-ring measurements in archaeological wood samples from X-ray computed tomography. *Dendrochronologia* 76, 126002.
- Mori, M., Kuhara, S., Suzuki, S., 2020. Visualizing the internal structure of polyethylene glycol-impregnated wood by digital breast tomosynthesis. *Dendrochronologia* 61, 125708.
- Okochi, T., 2016. A nondestructive dendrochronological study on Japanese wooden shinto art sculptures using micro-focus X-ray Computed Tomography (CT): Reviewing two methods for scanning objects of different sizes. *Dendrochronologia* 38, 1–10.
- Okochi, T., Fujii, H., Mitsutani, T., 2007. Nondestructive tree-ring measurements for Japanese oak and Japanese beech using micro-focus X-ray computed tomography. *Dendrochronologia* 24, 155–164.
- Onoe, M., Tsoo, J.W., Yamada, H., Nakamura, H., Kogure, J., Kawamura, H., Yoshimatsu, M., 1984. Computed tomography for measuring the annual rings of a live tree. *Nucl. Instrum. Methods Phys. Res.* 221, 213–220.
- Parent, J.M., 1985. The conservation of waterlogged wood using sucrose. *Stud. Conserv* 30, 63–72.
- Peli, E., 1990. Contrast in complex images. *J. Opt. Soc. Am. A* 7, 2032–2040.
- Sass, U., Eckstein, D., 1994. Preparation of large thin sections and surfaces of wood for automatic image analysis. *Holzforschung* 48, 117–118.
- Sass-Klaassen, U., Vernimmen, T., Baittinger, C., 2008. Dendrochronological dating and provenancing of timber used as foundation piles under historic buildings in The Netherlands. *Int. Biodeterior. Biodegrad.* 61, 96–105.
- Schmidt-Ott, K., André, C., Bader, P., 2022. Fishing for Stability: Conserving a Fish Trap in a Block Excavation by the Alcohol-Ether-Resin Method, in: Williams, E. (ed.), *Proceedings of the 14th ICOM-CC Wet Organic Archaeological Materials Working Group Conference*, Portsmouth, 2019. ICOM-CC WOAM, Portsmouth, pp. 322–327.
- Schweingruber, F.H., 2001. *Dendroökologische Holzanatomie. Anatomische Grundlagen der Dendrochronologie*. Verl. Paul. Haupt, Bern.

- Smith, C.W., 2003. Archaeological Conservation Using Polymers: Practical Applications for Organic Artifact Stabilization. Texas A&M University Press, College Station.
- Speer, J.H., 2010. Fundamentals of Tree-ring Research. University of Arizona Press, Tucson.
- Stelzner, I., Stelzner, J., Martinez-Garcia, J., Gwerder, D., Schuetz, P., 2023. Imaging and Assessment of the Microstructure of Conserved Archaeological Pine. *Forests* 14, 211. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f14020211>.
- Stelzner, I., Stelzner, J., Martinez-Garcia, J., Gwerder, D., Wittkoepper, M., Muskalla, W., Egg, M., Schuetz, P., 2021. Non-destructive assessment of conserved archaeological wood using computed tomography. In: Bridgland, J. (Ed.), *Transcending boundaries: integrated approaches to conservation. ICOM-CC 19th Triennial Conference preprints, Beijing, 2021. ICOM-CC, Paris*, pp. 1–11.
- Stelzner, J., Million, S., 2015. X-ray computed tomography for anatomical and dendrochronological analysis of archaeological wood. *J. Archaeol. Sci.* 55, 188–196.
- Stelzner, J., Stelzner, I., Martinez-Garcia, J., Gwerder, D., Million, S., Nelle O., Schuetz, P., in press. Non-destructive dendrochronology: the effect of conservation agents on tree-ring measurements in archaeological oak with micro-computed tomography. *J. Am. Inst. Conserv.*
- Stelzner, J., Stelzner, I., Martinez-Garcia, J., Gwerder, D., Wittkoepper, M., Muskalla, W., Cramer, A., Heinz, G., Egg, M., Schuetz, P., 2022. Stabilisation of waterlogged archaeological wood: the application of structured-light 3D scanning and micro computed tomography for analysing dimensional changes. *Herit. Sci.* 10, 1–25.
- Towner, R.H., 2002. Archeological dendrochronology in the southwestern united states. *Evol. Anthropol.* 11, 68–84.
- Van den Bulcke, J., Wernersson, E.L.G., Dierick, M., Van Loo, D., Masschaele, B., Brabant, L., Boone, M.N., Van Hoorebeke, L., Haneca, K., Brun, A., Hendriks, C.L.L., Van Acker, J., 2014. 3D tree-ring analysis using helical X-ray tomography. *Dendrochronologia* 32, 39–46.
- Vannoppen, A., Maes, S., Kint, V., De Mil, T., Ponette, Q., Van Acker, J., Van den Bulcke, J., Verheyen, K., Muys, B., 2017. Using X-ray CT based tree-ring width data for tree growth trend analysis. *Dendrochronologia* 44, 66–75.
- Wagenführ, R. *Holzatlas*, 4., neubearb. Aufl.; Fachbuchverl.: Leipzig, 1996.
- Walsh, Z., Janeček, E.-R., Jones, M., Scherman, O.A., 2017. Natural polymers as alternative consolidants for the preservation of waterlogged archaeological wood. *Stud. Conserv* 62, 173–183.
- Walsh, Z., Janeček, E.-R., Hodgkinson, J.T., Sedlmair, J., Koutsoubas, A., Spring, D.R., Welch, M., Hirschmugl, C.J., Toprakcioglu, C., Nitschke, J.R., Jones, M., Scherman, O.A., 2014. Multifunctional supramolecular polymer networks as next-generation consolidants for archaeological wood conservation. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 111, 17743–17748.
- Westphal, T., Heußner, K.U., 2016. Kleiner Leitfaden für den Umgang mit Holz für dendrochronologische Altersbestimmung. Dr. Friedrich Pfeil, München.
- Wiesner, I., Stelzner, J., Million, S., Kuhnt, K., Bott, K., 2016. The first wheels go round again. In: Grant, T., Cook, C. (Eds.), *Proc. 12th ICOM-CC Group Wet. Org. Archaeol. Mater. Conf., Istanbul, 2013. Lulu. Com., Istanbul*. 197–198.
- Withers, P.J., Bouman, C., Carmignato, S., Cnudde, V., Grimaldi, D., Hagen, C.K., Maire, E., Manley, M., Du Plessis, A., Stock, S.R., 2021. X-ray Comput. Tomogr. *Nat. Rev. Methods Prim.* 1, 1–21.
- Wittkoepper, M., 1998. Der aktuelle Stand der Holzkonservierung mit Melamin / Aminoharzen am Römisch-Germanischen Zentralmuseum. *Arb. für Restaur.* 29, 227–238.
- Wittkoepper, M., Muskalla, W., Stephan, B., Le Boedec-Moesgard, A., Gebhardt, S., Klöck, S., 2016. The KUR (conservation and restauration) project - a comparison of different methods to preserve waterlogged wood. *Proc. 12th ICOM-CC Group Wet. Org. Archaeol. Mater. Conf., Istanbul, 2013. Lulu. Com., Istanbul*. 134–143.